

MAIN ISSUES OF FINANCING SOCIAL EXPENDITURES

Turaev Ochil Yarasevich

Researcher

Annotation. Budgets vary depending on the direction of spending. If the costs of the economy and management are high, this means radical changes in the country's macroeconomic policy. In fact, the state budget must be socialized in essence; for this, domestic investments must be stimulated, and due to this, state costs in the economy must be reduced and its socialization increased. This process is the socialization of the budget process of Uzbekistan and has its own characteristics. This dissertation highlights the main directions of the socialized budget and issues of further improvement of the process in this direction.

Keywords. State budget, social expenditures, socialized budget, education expenditures, expenses, financing, social sector, healthcare. general education, school, cost estimates, first-level budget allocators, second-level budget allocators.

Every year in Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Economy and Finance, in accordance with the Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, develops the State Budget, which is a document that defines the main directions of the country's socio-economic development for the future period. Uzbekistan. It includes macroeconomic indicators for the medium term, forecasts of income and expenditure of the consolidated budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its deficit, information on sources of financing the deficit, the main directions of fiscal policy, and macroeconomic indicators. budget risks and analysis of public debt reforms planned to develop and improve public financial management, including increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of budget expenditures, ensuring budget openness, harmonizing expenditures with sustainable development goals, reforms aimed at the transition to "green" development. economics and budgeting, as well as improving internal control and internal audit in the public sector includes measures that need to be implemented to

To achieve macroeconomic and fiscal stability in the long term, the deficit needs to be reduced to an average of 3 percent over the medium term. To ensure that it does not exceed, it will be necessary to gradually reduce the size of the deficit by optimizing budget funds, expanding the revenue base, and eliminating ineffective tax breaks and preferences. Due to the fact that the upper limit of the budget deficit in 2024 is set at 4 percent, the amount of external debt raised to finance investment projects will be maintained, and the limited amount of external debt to be raised will be US\$5.0 billion. US dollars , of which 2.5 billion US dollars State budget support,

including financing of the budget deficit, the rest is aimed at financing investment projects .

At the same time, in order to diversify the public debt portfolio and reduce currency risks, the limited net volume of government securities that will be issued on behalf of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024 is set at 25 trillion soums (in 2023 - 17 trillion soums). . In order to ensure the growth of the economy of Uzbekistan within the forecast indicators, a fiscal policy that is flexible to external and internal influences is being implemented, aimed at ensuring macroeconomic and budgetary stability. In this case, it will be necessary to maintain public debt at a safe level for macroeconomic stability, not to increase the consolidated budget deficit compared to the approved forecast, to improve the system for assessing macro-fiscal risks, and to ensure that the consolidated budget is fully covered. , ensuring openness at all stages of the budget process and other similar promising areas.

Despite the difficult situation observed in the global economy over the past 4 years, as a result of reforms aimed at liberalizing the economy, in the country's development strategies and the implementation of programs aimed at developing industries, industries and regions, stable rates of economic growth in 2023 are ensured 5. 8 percent. Financing the economy and demand factors (demand coefficient) at the end of the current year, consolidated budget expenditures increased by 18.4 percent compared to the corresponding period last year , amounting to 380.9 trillion soums , which served as a stimulating factor for economic growth.

Table 1.

Wages and equivalent payments, billion soums

	202 3 years	202 forecast for 4 years	Difference	
			in total	in percentages
I. From the state budget	1 30 633	1 5 7 569	+2 6 936	+ 2 0 , 6
Share of the state budget in total expenditures, percentage	46 , 3	50 , 4	-	-
1. Wages and social tax	1 08 152	13 3 355	+2 5 203	+2 2 , 8
2 . Scholarships	1,597	1,958	+361	+22.6
3 . Social benefits	16 479	17,593	+ 1 114	+ 6.8
II. From the pension fund	5 3 8 53	63 137	9 284	+1 7.2
GENERAL	18 4 486	22 0 707	3 6 221	+ 19.6

Source: compiled by the author based on information from the Ministry of Finance and Economy.

From Table 1 it can be seen that in order to improve the standard of living of the population and ensure the growth of real incomes of citizens, wages and pensions are increasing every year. The socialization of the state budget is evidenced by the increase in wages in 2024 compared to 2023 by 22.6 percent or 361 trillion soums. If wages increase, this will affect the purchasing power of the population, since measures associated with reducing inflation to single digits will increase the purchasing power of the population as a result of such wage increases.

Another indicator characterizing the socialization of the state budget is the increase in the volume of funds allocated to finance educational loans. In 2021-2023, 3.3 trillion soums of resource funds were allocated for educational loans to a total of 315 thousand students , of which 219 thousand are women. Additionally, in 2024, funds are planned to provide educational loans to 180 thousand students, and the number of students covered by this program is expected to reach 500 thousand . 2.2 trillion soums are planned for these purposes in 2024 , of which 1.8 trillion soums will be used to finance education loans and 400 billion soums to cover the percentage of loans allocated to women.

Table 2.

Main indicators of secondary general education organizations

	20 20 years	2021	2022	2023	202 4 years
Total number of organizations, units.	10 193	10,292	10,507	10 520	10,620
secondary schools	9,920	9,924	9,959	9,972	10,072
boarding schools	227	231	227	227	227
orphanages	117	121	127	127	127
Presidential schools	-	4	14	14	14
creativity and specialized schools	-	12	180	180	180
students (thousands)	5995	6,280.2	6,405.9	6,534.0	6 666 , 9
current expenses (billion soums)	22,365.4	27,247.7	33,137.7	38,279.1	4 2 894.0
of which: per student (million soums)	3.7	4.3	5, 2	5, 8	6 , 4
Capital expenditures	3,365.0	3,374.0	3 029 , 2	2 760.2	4 100.0

Source: compiled by the author based on information from the Ministry of Finance and Economy.

In 2024, it is planned to allocate 13.5 trillion soums from the state budget to finance preschool education organizations, which is 14.0 percent more than planned

in 2023. At the same time, the bulk of expenses, that is, 51 percent, is allocated to wages and social tax expenses. It is planned to spend 42.9 trillion soums , or 12.1% more than the planned execution in 2023, to allocate 13.7% of the total expenditures of the State budget. At the same time, the main part of expenses, that is, 88 percent, falls on wages and social tax expenses.

In our opinion, in addition to the above, in order to increase the sociality of the State budget, it is advisable to pay special attention to the following:

It is necessary to improve the current criteria for determining the status of a low-income family. According to a survey conducted jointly with the World Bank, 14 percent of households in our country are classified as low-income. 23 percent of families receive social payments through the Unified Register of Social Protection. It is necessary to reach really needy families with the system of social benefits by improving the current criteria for payment of benefits;

From 2024, it is advisable to transfer child benefits and material assistance to low-income families from funding from the relevant local budgets to funding from the republican budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

To fully finance activities in the field of social protection, we believe that it is necessary to generate expenses of the National Social Protection Agency in the amount of 3.3 trillion soums;

In 2024, 1.5 trillion soums of subsidies should be paid from the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan to cover part of the down payment and interest on mortgage loans to citizens with low incomes and in need of improved housing conditions. Effective use of available financial resources in higher education institutions.

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